

Leadership identity development in classical and jazz music: Comparing life histories of eminent female musicians

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Abstract

This paper aims at understanding the factors influencing the leadership identity development of two eminent female musicians (pseudonyms: Elena, Tinecia), as a conductor and a composer respectively, in classical and jazz music. They are also educational leaders in the higher music education institutes in the United Kingdom and the United States. Using theories of leadership identity, social identity, social stratification, and intersectionality, the paper revealed significant factors for the two female musicians' musical learning and professional development embedded in the formal and informal social structures in classical and jazz music. It examined and compared critical incidents and modal trajectories contributing to the leadership identity establishment in the life histories of both female musicians, and identified relevant issues in music education, industry, and wider societies inhibiting or facilitating women's leadership identity establishments and dynamics in music. The paper posited that leadership identities are multi-layered, subject to intersected social forces, and malleable throughout lives. It concluded with theoretical findings on leadership identity development in music and practical implications for music education and professional development.

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Key words

leadership identity, life history research, intersectionality, cross-cultural comparison

Introduction

Across different cultures, “leaders are widely recognized as the proper focus for our attempts to understand the tides and shape of history” (Haslam et al., 2020, p. 1), so life histories of leaders enhance our understandings of leadership identity development in various social contexts, including art, technology, and education. Life history research recognises that “social and personal realities originate in the dialogical relationship between individuals and groups and the values and practices which characterise social worlds” (Goodson & Sikes, 2001, p. 112). This is accomplished by studying “the trajectory of our lives” in the past, which brings us to “a confrontation with identity” at the present where “private troubles and public issues collide” (Downs, 2016, p. 603). These issues serve as the foci of the life history research, e.g., to analyse the “critical incidents” (Patton, 2014, p. 404) and “modal trajectories” (Bourdieu, 1984, p. 110) of the two eminent female musicians’ life histories. This paper focuses on the processes of their leadership identity establishment.

Theoretical framework

A person has multiple identities, each constructed in the interpersonal relation and collective membership of a social context (Worchel & Austin, 1986; Jenkins, 2008). This also applies to leadership identity which is more “ambiguous, dynamic, and contextual” compared to other identities (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 630). Traditional theories on leadership perceived it as an individualistic trait of people “born with special gift or talent” (Howe, 2001, p. 76), which set “the minds and lives of leaders apart from those of others” (Haslam et al., 2020, p. 1). However, this did not consider “patterns of influence” for leadership identity or “social processes in its creation” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 630). Furthermore, traditional views focused on social contexts where the roles of leader and “subordinates” (ibid., p. 640) were “designated” (ibid., p. 635), and the field structure was “hierarchical” and “static” (ibid., p.

629); so other contexts were underexplored.

Contrarily, Haslam, Reicher, and Platow (2020) posited leadership identity as “grounded in leaders’ capacity to embody and promote a psychology that they share with others” (p. 2). This entails a “tripartite” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 628) identification system including “individual internalisation”, “relational recognition”, and “collective endorsement” (ibid., p. 631). Individual internalisation refers to the self-recognition of the leadership, which does not establish the leadership identity unless coupled with “relational recognition” – “the adoption of reciprocal role identities as leader and follower” (ibid., p. 628). Leadership identity is constructed when “others take on a reciprocal follower identity” in groups whereas hierarchies and assigned positions do not guarantee relational recognition (ibid., p. 629). Further, when leader of a social group is supported and endorsed in the broader social environment, he or she achieves “collective endorsement” (ibid., p. 631). The tripartite identifications fulfil and “reinforce” leadership identity, making it “stronger and more stable” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 629).

Leadership identity is established through “leadership legitimacy” (William, 1986, p. 163), i.e., when follower “claims” leader and leader “grants” follower (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 631). Both informal and formal social structures influence the legitimation of leadership identity in music. Informal structure includes “social stratification, status hierarchies, social networks, cultural norms and values, and sub-group leadership responsibilities” (ibid., p. 642), which can influence the musical learning and professional development of musicians (Wright, 2015). To analyse the informal structure in music, I use the concepts of schema, disposition, and habitus. Schema means musically-related social meaning and practice “inculcated and conserved in memory as knowledge” (Bourdieu, 1984, p. 67). It forms

“patterns of behaviour consistent with previous experiences and future projections” (Wright, 2015, p. 81) and develop “habitual responses” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 636) in leadership actions and relations. Leadership-structure schema refers to one’s conceptualisation of leadership within a social context, e.g., whether the leadership can be shared and “mutually enacted among group members” (“participative” leadership style), or there is “only one leader in a group” and “leader and follower identities are mutually exclusive” (“authoritative” leadership style) (ibid., pp. 633 & 639).

Disposition means “schemes of perception, appreciation, and action” directing “social uses of objects” (Bourdieu, 1984, p. 570), e.g., how to play musical instruments or move the baton for conducting. Through musical learning and practices, the socialised dispositions become attached to the music “technical objects”, constructing “habitus” in music fields (ibid., p. 29), e.g., the ways for notation reading or improvisation (Burwell, 2023; Hultberg, 2010). In genres such as classical and jazz music, when dispositions are oriented toward capitals that privilege some social members, they become habitus embodied and transmitted in social relations and music groups. Habitus could be “engendered by history” and passed on across generations and cultures (Bourdieu, 1977, p. 82). For example, Perkins (2015) revealed that habitus can “shape the ways in which [beginning career] musicians view and experience their career preparation” (p. 102), while Sagiv and Hall (2015) identified habitus as constantly displayed in the bodily movements and cultural knowledge of the classical musicians, making explicit the “strict rules, demanding norms and conservative conventions” of the classical music field (p. 114).

Formal social structure lies in schools, educational institutions, professional organisations, etc., manifested in curriculum, pedagogy, and the social conduct of gatekeepers that define

and affirm “generalised expectations” of leadership in music (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 640). These expectations originate from “implicit theories of leadership”, i.e., other identities of the person that attach social meanings to the leadership identity (ibid.). When conflicting social meanings are integrated into the leadership identity, there might exist intersected inequalities. For example, legitimising leadership identity was challenging for leaders who were female and/or racial minorities in the United States because there were “evidence[s] of race and gender hierarchies in the legislature” (Wilson, 2013, p. 28; also, Crenshaw, 1989).

Both leadership-structure schema and implicit theories of leadership originate from social members’ past experiences of leadership and “followership” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 637). If one has been used to experiencing the participative or authoritative leadership style, he or she might establish a corresponding image of leadership and develop conscious or unconscious “behavioural response patterns” (DeRue & Ashford, 2010, p. 636), forming “habitual responses enacted in future situations with minimal thought and effort” (ibid.). Therefore, studying the life histories of the two female musicians and leaders contributes an in-depth understanding of the factors embedded in the practices (schema, disposition, habitus) and (formal and informal) structures of the classical and jazz music fields, which have influenced their leadership identity establishment (Bourdieu, 1977, 1984; DeRue & Ashford, 2010; Perkins, 2015; Sagiv & Hall, 2015).

Data analysis

Elena (pseudonym) is an internationally renowned female classical music conductor. She is the leader of a reputed opera company and the conducting department of an esteemed music conservatoire in the United Kingdom.

Tinecia (pseudonym) is a world-famous female jazz drummer and composer. She has won various awards including the Grammys. She is the founder of a music institute in a well-known music college in the United States.

Childhood and adolescence

Elena's musical journey began with piano lessons at a young age, supported by her mixed-ethnic family. A large-scale music festival sparked her interest in a brass instrument, which she pursued at a new school that "had all [musical] instruments", after her family moved from a village to a city. Her music teacher introduced her to two youth orchestras, including a "prestigious" and "free-standing" one whose "more senior" members "came [to her home] and [they] rehearsed in the afternoon" until her mother made dinner for them before the concert. Elena's passion and dedication earned her a scholarship to study instrumental performance at a reputed conservatoire.

Elena's life experiences at childhood showed that the dispositions and supports of her family, teacher(s), and peer groups were her musical starting point (Baker & Green, 2017), while the youth orchestras provided initial social contexts where her leadership in music emerged.

Constituted through collaborative music making with peers, her initial leadership integrated social and cultural capitals and two dispositions: moving geographically and earning financial support. Thus, ethnic, social-relational, social-economic, and musical identities were integrated into the early development of Elena's leadership identity.

Tinecia, raised in a family of African-American musicians, was encouraged to play music from a young age because "the drums were there. My father played it, and my grandfather too". While she heard stories of students "in [all levels of] school[s] steered away from certain

instruments and did not get solos or [other] opportunities”, she avoided these biases through private tutoring by her family. After performing at a major jazz festival, she received a full scholarship to an elite music college, where she studied with first-class jazz musicians. She has released over ten albums.

Tinecia’s family supported her to connect with expert musicians in jazz music, where the performance-based culture entailed “monolithic”, “admiration-based”, and chain-referral habitus and structure (Johansen, 2023, p. 7). This enabled her to master the “improvisation performance practices” (Lohmeyer, 2023, p. 12), which could to some extent offset the identity-based challenges in her leaning and working environment. For example, she “functioned well in a male-dominated space”, and this meant that her mastery of the musical practices could earn her more equal and respectful professional relations with her male colleagues in jazz music. With these social and cultural capitals, Tinecia developed a strong followership identity and an initial (participative) leadership-structure schema.

As above, during childhood and adolescence, both Elena and Tinecia gained substantial social and cultural capitals before they entered the higher education, but with different approaches. Tinecia inherited the family’s capitals and Elena earned them through cultivating relations with teachers and peers. These influenced their early forms of leadership-structure schema, which for Elena it comprised of sub-group leaderships in various music groups (DeRue & Ashford, 2010), and for Tinecia it consisted of close associations with master performers and “embodied expertise of jazz composers” (Burwell, 2023, p. 10). The different foundations of leadership-structure schema might have contributed to the different leadership identity development in the two female musicians’ lives, as I continue to analyse their adulthood

experiences.

Young adulthood

From mid-adolescence, Elena's instrument teacher was a "famous [and] virtuous" musician. She followed the teacher to a respected conservatoire but he left the teaching position soon after her enrolment. Without the teacher, but feeling "wanted the music so much", Elena "invit[ed] friends to come and play" in self-organized concerts and achieved "more or less success". Later she won a scholarship to study a postgraduate diploma in conducting at the same conservatory and met an Estonian conductor at a summer course. She asked him "how can I learn to conduct like you" and he recommended studying in Leningrad where he was trained. Although her parents concerned that "there was not a general picture of women naturally becoming conductors", they supported her living costs at her postgraduate study, believing that "somebody somewhere must think [she has] got potential".

The postgraduate curriculum let Elena feel in limbo "between being a student and [a] junior member of staff", with "more non-academic responsibilities" than she liked and less "intensive teaching". She persuaded another conservatoire to include her "as [an] additional student" in a class led by a "wonderful conductor and musicologist". With her peers, she followed the routine "in [typical European] music schools", i.e., playing for each other from the score and took turns "conducting in the middle". Following this pedagogy, Elena worried that she did not learn how to "move your hands and use the baton".

Elena embodied dispositions to enter an elite music education institute and followed the famous musician as her teacher. Because the bias against a conductor's innate ability — "all conductors are born not made" — prevailed in classical music, she conceptualised the field as

hierarchical, thus endorsed a followership identity and authoritative leadership-structure schema. These were thwarted when her teacher discontinued the support, and she had to seek for peer-learning and support in music groups. This gained her relational recognition and fostered an emerging participative leadership-structure schema (DeRue & Ashford, 2010).

During the “two difficult years” of her postgraduate study, the support from Elena’s family and external institution somewhat offset the biases (against gender and innate ability), and the institutional barriers (curriculum and pedagogy). This maintained a strong followership identity for Elena, until she found the conducting class lacked diversity in student membership, then she decided to follow the advice of the Estonian conductor. She seemed to not believe that the classical music field could only be hierarchical, which motivated her to change to a different leadership-structure schema and enrolled in a conducting programme in the Soviet Union.

As a young female jazz drummer and producer, Tinecia realised that “people think more about keyboard players and melodic instrument players as producers and composers”. This originated from the historical “pitch-focused worldview” (Bauer et al., 2021, p. 8) that some instrumentalists, e.g., drummers, had inferior abilities to others. This bias intersected with biases against gender (she did not “always get the same respect [as her] male counterparts”) and other identities (she felt “a glass ceiling” for female producers) to hinder her leadership development. Tinecia co-produced early albums with renowned jazz musicians but was not the leading composer. Both young Tinecia and Elena maintained strong followership identities in both music fields, but because inequalities (biases against gender identity, innate ability, and institutional barriers), they developed leadership identities different from their precedents

(e.g., other female musicians in my PhD study).

Leadership identity establishment

Elena did not learn the Russian language in advance since she was uncertain whether the application would be successful. But after arriving in the Soviet Union, she could join the Russian language course without taking the examinations mandatory for her fellow students from Soviet Satellite states) and enjoyed additional accesses (“surrounded by [peers] who wanted to try their English with an English speaker”). These gave her exemptions from the rules and provided her social and cultural capitals.

Originally assigned to “the father of a famous conductor” and “was not allowed to choose other teachers”, she managed to enter the class with “the head of the department” through a classmate at the language course. Within the “big conducting department” teachers used formal languages to communicate. Elena’s class worked with a “fully professional orchestra” regularly where she had “fifteen minutes” to “try up with the orchestra”; and senior students had more time. The curriculum and pedagogy addressed individual needs of students and created an environment where “everybody knew exactly where they were” and a “real sense of building towards [conducting] with the orchestra”. These satisfied Elena’s learning needs and enhanced her leadership identities in both conducting and music education.

Among the few female conductors in both countries, Elena did not find being in the “men’s world” an issue until she felt the difficulty to decide “what clothes [to] wear” for conducting. In Britain, “when men wear tailcoats, women would wear beautiful cocktail dresses [with] no sleeves and high heels [which] would be hopeless for conducting”. This denoted that the social meanings of Elena’s gender or social-economic identities could not align with her

conductor identity. A fellow female conductor in the Soviet Union was “always smartly dressed [in] a suit with a skirt” which she could not identify with either (could not align with Elena’s cultural identity). She also disliked the image of domestic female politician, i.e., “power dressing” with “enormous shoulders, highly tailored suits [and] skirts” (did not align with her political identity). Moreover, another female conductor wearing “tail suit” but Elena doubted whether she was “trying to be conducting like a man” (did not align with her gender identity).

Elena “used to wear a long skirt” until a concert master said, “If you wear skirts, I cannot see your knees, which I am in the pit looking at to see when to make the first upbeat”. She said, “Good! I am wearing trousers from now on”. However, this remained “a continuing issue for women conductors”. As Elena’s experiences evidenced, the gender, social-economic, cultural, and political norms have been contributing to the intersectional challenges for establishing women’s professional images and identities in conducting. Therefore, her leadership identity in conducting integrated with her social-economic, gender, political, and cultural identities.

Tinecia identified several barriers for women to “evolve” in jazz. Apart from the aforementioned instrument-related biases in the “education system”, social gender behaviours also created “chatters” and “micro-aggressions” to make young female musicians feeling “like minorities”. Also, mentoring was inadequate especially if “successful [musicians], mostly men” do not mentor girls and young women. Thus, the intersection among the chain-referral culture and the gender- and race-based social divisions of labour (Johansen, 2023; Lohmeyer, 2023) “permeate all areas that [a musician] work”, making Tinecia aware that “I was not helping in the way [to] address these issues”. This awareness enhanced her leadership identity in music education, while her leadership in composition was not established until she “paid

[for] [an album] and made it happen [by herself]”. Tinecia called for “compassion for the whole [society]” instead of “only caring about [own] group”; and this showed a collective endorsement (DeRue & Ashford, 2010). Therefore, social-economic, gender, and cultural identities were integrated into Tinecia’s leadership identity in both music education and composition.

Conclusion

The analysis above proved that leadership identities of both female musicians (Elena and Tinecia) arose from their experiences in multiple contexts and music fields, where social-economic, ethnic, gender, racial, cultural, and political identities were integrated and intersected. This intersectionality might cause indefinite leadership image, ambiguous leadership-structure schema, or unsuccessful leadership identity establishment.

Tinecia’s leadership identities in music composition and education were formed in relational recognition (working with jazz experts), established with individual internalisation (self-initiated album), and enhanced through collective endorsement (founding and leading a music institute). Her two leadership identities were co-developed and highly compatible. Elena’s leadership identities in music conducting and education started from relational recognition (learning with music peer-groups) to individual internalisation (leading the conducting department). Her experiences in the two social and cultural contexts with distinctive formal and informal structures did not facilitate collective endorsement since she could not identify a professional image with any female conductor or leader cross-culturally.

Therefore, the most accomplished leadership identity in music would achieve all three-levels of the tripartite identifications (DeRue & Ashford, 2010), and if there are multiple

professional trajectories, different leadership identities need to be co-constructed throughout the different life contexts and keep its consistency and congruency. Furthermore, it is possible that the more diverse social and cultural contexts one had experienced, the more complex one's leadership identity can be (such as Elena); but whether the complexity could solidify or scatter the leadership identity remains uncertain.

Future research into the leadership of women and/or other minorities in orchestral and choral conducting, in classical or jazz compositions, in composition or production, etc., might be helpful to further understand the relations between field structure and leadership development in music. It is also worth studying the intersectionality among cultural, social-economic, leadership, and musical identities to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the relations and structures of different music fields and social/cultural contexts. Finally, the life histories of two female musicians informed the necessities to be aware of the intersected inequalities across music fields and to support students from minority backgrounds, as well as to consider the social meanings of leadership in accordance with the different cultural backgrounds of students in various music learning contexts.

Limitations

This paper could not have presented more detailed processes of the leadership identity development of the two female musicians, drawn on more original data, or included the life histories of other female musicians in my PhD study, due to the limited space. In addition, I have only illustrated and analysed parts of the life histories of the two female musicians, and my comparison between the two life histories was rather brief. More in-depth analysis and multiple layers of comparison could be considered for future life history studies in music.

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